

Digital Support for physics service lectures

Kevin Schmitt, Verena Spatz¹

Abstract: It has been shown repeatedly that students' understanding of physics concepts often remains fragmentary, even after traditional instruction. Against this background, a STACK-based digital learning environment has been designed, that can be used as an online course to enrich physics lectures for engineering students at TU Darmstadt. This course serves two main purposes: First, as an analytic aspect of the project, data on the students' perspective and knowledge at the start of the semester is collected. This data can be useful to inform topic selection and pedagogical approaches for the lecture to better address the challenges that they face. Second, as a supporting aspect of the project, a differentiated learning opportunity is offered for self-study during the semester in a blended-learning format of the course in addition to the lecture.

Keywords: STACK; Physics for Engineering Faculty; E-Learning; TU Darmstadt; online course

1 Motivation

After the transition into university, students face manifold challenges of different dimensions. In addition to organizational structures and processes within the university, they also have to get familiar with media literacy skills needed to take full advantage of the offered courses [IK09]. Moreover, many students need to close knowledge gaps of fundamentals that are required for university lectures [AW14]. Therefore, supplement courses are deemed a promising measure to help cross these hurdles and online implementation becomes increasingly popular - a situation which is reinforced by the current Covid-19 virus outbreak. A goal often associated with this is to give students the possibility to get along quickly with the specific work and study practices at the university [Re14].

On those grounds, a project has been initiated at TU Darmstadt to design and evaluate a STACK-based online course to enrich physics lectures for engineering students, targeted to be available for the summer term 2020. The project is part of "digLL – Digital gestütztes Lehren und Lernen in Hessen", a collaboration of eleven German universities developing innovative concepts for "Digitally supported Teaching and Learning in Hesse" funded by the Ministry of Science and Art. In this paper we will give a short, high-level summary of the project. In the second section, the goals of the course will be unfolded. In the third paragraph, its implementation will be described. Since efforts to develop online courses for the subject of physics are already being made in several projects in Germany, we will focus on the use of STACK on the platform "Moodle" and its added value from a media-didactical point of view [Sa15].

¹Technische Universität Darmstadt, Physics Education, Hochschulstraße 12, 64289 Darmstadt, Germany
kevin.schmitt@physik.tu-darmstadt.de, verena.spatz@physik.tu-darmstadt.de

2 Goals of the course

The goals of the course must be outlined in two respects: The course assesses students' perspective and knowledge about the syllabus of the respective lecture at the start of the semester to provide a basis for topic selection and pedagogical approaches in order to meet students' needs (analytic aspect). The course also offers a differentiated learning opportunity for self-study in addition to the lecture (supporting aspect).

To tailor the contents of the course to the relevant audiences, a survey in the engineering department has been carried out additionally, including faculty as well as students, about the precise contents and skills that they feel to be particularly important in physics. Summarizing the results of the survey, high priority is placed on the following five dimensions of requirement: 1) basic- and prior-knowledge, 2) understanding of physical relationships, 3) mathematical skills, 4) interpretation of experiments/phenomena and 5) understanding of physical derivation.

3 Implementation of the course

The course is integrated in the platform "Moodle", used as the central element for the organization of many lectures and seminars at TU Darmstadt. The STACK tool is used for task creation and verification. STACK provides to combine multiple-choice questions (MC-questions) and arithmetic problems. Therefore, correct solutions require a rather broad range of skills and are checked not only for physical units but also for mathematical properties. Another useful application of STACK is the utilization of interactive graphs by means of JSXGraph, based on a JavaScript [Ba21]. Answering within interactive graphs promotes conceptual understanding while exploiting the full potentialities of multimedia learning [Ma01]. This is particularly profitable for physical contents that have to be visualized, e.g. in the field of geometrical optics.

4 Conclusion and outlook

The ongoing development of the course, that will be extended to other lectures in the future, goes hand-in-hand with the advancement of the STACK tool. Especially in the light of the current boom of digital teaching and learning formats, evoked by the shutdown of many universities due to the Covid-19 pandemic, we regard the potential of the project more important today than ever.

Bibliography

- [AW14] Abel, H.; Weber, B.: 28 Jahre Esslinger Modell – Studienanfänger und Mathematik. In: Bausch, I. et al. (Hrsg): Mathematische Vor- und Brückenkurse. Konzepte und Studien zur Hochschuldidaktik und Lehrerbildung Mathematik, Springer Spektrum, Wiesbaden 2014.
- [Ba21] Bayreuth, University: Homepage of the University of Bayreuth for the application JSXGraph: <https://jsxgraph.uni-bayreuth.de/wp/index.html>. 04/2021.
- [IK09] Issing, L. J.; Klimsa, P. (Hrsg): Online Lernen: Handbuch für Wissenschaft und Praxis, Oldenbourg Verlag München. 2009.
- [Ma01] Mayer, R. E.: Multimedia Learning, Cambridge University Press. 2001.
- [Re14] Reichersdorfer, E.; Ufer, S.; Lindmeier, A.; Reiss, K.: Der Übergang von der Schule zur Universität: Theoretische Fundierung und praktische Umsetzung Unterstützungsmaßnahme am Beginn des Mathematikstudiums. In: Bausch, I. et al. (Hrsg): Mathematische Vor- und Brückenkurse. Konzepte und Studien zur Hochschuldidaktik und Lehrerbildung Mathematik, Springer Spektrum, Wiesbaden. 2014.
- [Sa15] Sangwin, C. J.: Who uses STACK? A survey of users of the STACK CAA system, Loughborough University, June. 2015.